

STANISLAV SHINKARENKO^{1,2*}, ASEL BERDENGALIEVA²

Geoinformation mapping of fire-damaged areas in saiga habitat in the North-Western pre-Caspian area of Russia

Landscape fires are a significant factor determining the dynamics of grassy ecosystems across the world. Fires not only destroy vegetation and soil, but also decrease the accumulation of plant seeds in the soil, change the thermodynamic properties of the earth's surface, reduce the humidity of upper soil layers, and intensify erosion processes. Regular fires in the steppe also lead to changes in vegetation composition, increasing the proportion of turf cereals resistant to fire and displacing semi-shrubs, which inevitably affects herbivore populations. The destruction of vegetation by fire also forces animals to migrate in search of food. In some years, steppe fires in the North-Western pre-Caspian region cover more than 1.5–2 million

hectares, which could negatively affect herbivores, including saigas.

To specify the spatial and temporal patterns of fire distribution within saiga habitat in this region (administratively, the Republic of Kalmykia and the portion of Astrakhan province on the right bank of the Volga), we decrypted Landsat satellite images from 1984 to 2021, which are publicly available on the portal of the US Geological Survey, and can also be downloaded using the Vega-Science service developed by the Space Research Institute of RAS. Two combinations of spectral channels were used (Fig. 1): 'natural colours', roughly showing how the image is visible by the human eye; and a combination with the infrared range included,

highlighting areas destroyed by fire. Satellite images were processed and decrypted using the free software QGIS. Archival data on fire sites, as well as all other available information on areas damaged by fire, were also used in the analysis. However, the most accurate results were obtained only with the help of experts who 'manually' identified burnt-up sites.

The analysis helped identify 3,976 fires over almost 40 years on a total area of 7.17 million hectares (Fig. 2), which means about one third of the region's territory had been affected by fire, with some sites having burnt more than 10 times. Over 90% of fires were recorded in summer and autumn. No fires were recorded in 1984–1988, which might be the result of a combination of factors such as a smaller number of cloudless satellite images and their poor quality, as well as a significantly smaller area affected by fire. The smaller fire area recorded between 1984 and 1990 is also confirmed by other studies. The increase in the area affected by fire since the early 1990s may be associated with growing livestock numbers, lower moisture levels, and shrinkage of arable land, leading

Fig. 1. Satellite image of a burnt-up site on 6th August 2006 (left – synthesis in natural colours, right – with the inclusion of near and short-wave infrared channels)

to the accumulation of dead plant remains and the intensification of fires. Catastrophic fires, each covering an area of more than 25,000 hectares, have been recorded from 1998 onwards. The largest ones, covering an area of more than 200,000 hectares (in 2000, 2002, 2006, 2007, 2011), took place in the Chernye Zemli Reserve and Stepnoy Zakaznik and adjacent territories. Between 1998 and 2011, more than 40–60% of these protected areas, which are core habitat for saigas, were destroyed by fire every 2–3 years. Certainly, this has affected the saigas living there. On average, in 1997–2008, up to 40% of the Chernye Zemli Reserve

and 25% of the Stepnoy Zakaznik were destroyed by fire annually. In 2006, the Chernye Zemli Reserve burnt almost completely, with 95% of its territory damaged by fire. After 2011, the number and area of steppe fires in the region decreased significantly (Fig. 3, 4), which is associated with the restoration of livestock numbers and aridification. This led to a decrease in the volume of dead plants, which resulted in the shrinkage of fire areas. The 2020 drought, caused by uncontrolled grazing, led to the almost complete destruction of vegetation by livestock, which is why only single, small, fire sites were recorded in 2020 and 2021 (Fig. 4). The area of fires in this

landscape depends primarily on combustible material – dry grass. Factors that reduce the amount of dead organic matter – grazing, higher temperatures and droughts – contribute to the reduction in the fire-affected area.

Saiga numbers sharply decreased in the region in 1997–1999, when the first catastrophic fires affected their habitats. After 2003–2004, saiga numbers in Kazakhstan tended to increase but the north-west pre-Caspian population did not. On the contrary, after 2010–2011, its numbers dropped to a minimum. This may be associated with the largest areas being damaged by fire in the Chernye Zemli Reserve

Fig. 2. Number of fires between 1984 and 2021 (a, I – number of fires, II – protected areas, III – district boundaries, IV – salt pans, V – lakes and canals, VI – paved roads) and duration of pyrogenic successions as of 2021 (b, I – succession duration, years, II – protected areas, III – district boundaries, IV – lakes and canals, V – paved roads)

Fig. 3. Comparison of fire sites in strictly protected natural areas in different periods

and adjacent territories between 1997 and 2008, when, probably, deprived of their foraging grounds, saigas migrated outside the protected areas, where they could become easy prey for poachers.

About 80% of the fires recorded within 10 kilometres and half within 20 kilometres of the Chernye Zemli Reserve eventually reached its territory. Approximately 70–75% of fires within the Steпnoy Zakaznik, located to the east of Chernye Zemli, came from adjoining territories indicates insufficient fire prevention measures at their borders and internally. In the Sarpinsky and Kharbinsky Zakazniks, for example, about half of the fires come from outside, while the rest break out inside the protected areas.

The pyrogenic transformation of plant communities resulting from regular fires in the study area, according to our personal observations and other surveys, leads to a decrease in the proportion of semi-shrubs (such as *Artemisia* spp., *Bassia* spp.) and various grass species in the vegetation, and the predominance of turf cereals (*Stipa* spp., *Festuca* spp., *Agropyron* spp.) and ephemera (for example, *Poa bulbosa* L., *Anisantha tectorum* L.), which are combustible after their growing season, in early-mid-summer. Similar pyrogenic changes are also recorded in savannas. Comparing the periods of pyrogenic successions, numbers of fire cases, results of geobotanical studies and meteorological data, as well as conducting additional studies, will in future allow for more accurate assessments of the contribution of fire to the dynamics of vegetation in saiga habitats.

Fig. 4. Dynamics of burnt areas and livestock numbers

The work carried out by our team has resulted in a local geoinformation system entitled ‘Landscape fires in saiga habitats in the north-west pre-Caspian Sea region.’ The study was accomplished with the support of WWF Russia under the WWF001671 project ‘Geoinformation mapping and analysis of the dynamics of landscape fire areas in the saiga habitat in the north-west pre-Caspian Sea region.’

¹ Space Research Institute, Russian Academy of Sciences, Moscow, Russia
² Federal Research Centre for Agroecology, Integrated Land Reclamation and Protective Afforestation, Russian Academy of Sciences, Volgograd, Russia
 * Corresponding author: shinkarenkos@vifanc.ru